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Sustainability through a gender lens: The extent to which research on UN Sustainable Development Goals includes sex and gender consideration

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Introduction

In recent years, there has been growing recognition of the benefits of incorporating sex and gender analysis into research, with calls for this dimension to be considered from the design stage (Heidari, Babor, De Castro et al., 2016), (ICMJE, 2019). By doing so, research questions will be answered more comprehensively and the research itself will be more robust and reproducible (Tannenbaum, Ellis, Eyssel et al., 2019).

It has also become evident, particularly through a report by UN Women (UN Women, 2018) and discussions at the Gender Summits (Gender Summits, 2016) (Lee & Pollitzer, 2016), and previous research (Hepp, Somerville & Borisch, 2019), that the targets for the United Nations' (UN) Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (United Nations, 2021) must be viewed from a gender perspective to ensure that gender-responsive policies and accountability processes are developed and the outcomes to achieve the goals benefit women and men equally.

Several of the SDGs are written with a recognition of the role of sex and gender in achieving outcomes and are specified in their targets and the indicators used to measure progress. But while the UN has recognized a need for “systematic mainstreaming of a gender perspective” (United Nations, 2015), this is not the case across all goals: one UN Women report identified cases where targets that included a gender dimension were lacking that dimension in the monitoring indicator (UN Women, 2018) and another reported insufficient data to enable comprehensive tracking of progress (UN Women, 2021). With SDG outcomes fixed to a 2030 target date, building an understanding of how sex and gender are embedded within the research

supporting the SDGs is an immediate imperative. To establish a baseline understanding based on published research studies, we have developed an approach to detect and visualize the volume and proportion of research publications that include explicit mention of sex and/or gender topics. In the rest of this paper we will outline this approach and highlight some key findings.

Methods

Expanding on previous studies that investigated gender in research from a topical perspective using the Scopus database (Elsevier, 2017), we developed a keyword search-based approach to identify publications that explicitly include terms related to sex and/or gender topical research. These publications are matched to the corpus of publications reflecting research related to each of 16 SDGs (excluding SDG 17: Partnership for the Goals) that have been defined on the basis of expert-informed Scopus keyword searches augmented with machine learning (Rivest, Kashnitsky, Bédard-Vallée, et al., 2021).

In this study we consider sex and gender together. Following the WHO's definitions, sex "refers to the biological characteristics that define humans as male or female," and gender "refers to the socially constructed norms, roles and relations of and among women, men, boys and girls," as well as the "expressions and identities of women, men, boys, girls and gender-diverse people" (World Health Organization, 2019). While separate concepts, they are related and the keyword search incorporates terms that relate to both. This allows for any interchangeable or perhaps incorrect use of terms .

The keyword-based approach to identify publications including terms related to sex and/or gender was created as follows. We captured relevant keywords from: i) keywords from publications within the public Mendeley library "Gender in the Global Research Landscape" (Elsevier, Gender in the Global Research Landscape Mendeley Group, 2017); ii) terms used by established organizations and societies, e.g. Gender Identity Research and Education Society, UNICEF and UNESCO; iii) and terms provided by Portia Ltd, the organizer of the Gender Summits. Each keyword was tested individually in a Scopus search of publication titles, abstracts and author/index keywords for precision and recall and appropriate wildcards, Boolean and proximity operators were identified for each. Keywords were excluded where their non-specificity resulted in decreased precision without any increase in recall. Publications were limited to those published in 2020, and to peer-reviewed types (i.e., articles, reviews, conference proceedings, short surveys and data articles). The final, selected Scopus sex and gender keyword search can be found in Table 1.

Table 1. The selected Scopus sex and gender keyword search.

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY(woman OR transgender* OR sexuality OR sexis* OR patriarch* OR neutrois
OR matrimon* OR matriarch* OR maternity OR maternal* OR paternity OR paternal* OR
masculin* OR intersectional* OR housewi*e* OR femini* OR {third sex} OR {men} OR
*gender* OR "son preference" OR "sexual object*" OR "sex traffick*" OR "non binary" OR
"human traffick*" OR "force* marriage*" OR "daughter preference" OR "child rear*" OR "sex*
affect*" OR "sex* biodivers*" OR sexing OR male OR female OR childbear* OR {sexes} OR
"sexual dimorph*" OR "sex* variat*" OR "sex* system*" OR "sex* select*" OR "sex* related
differen*" OR "sex* ratio*" OR "sex* preselect*" OR "sex* matur*" OR "sex* identif*" OR "sex*
factor*" OR "sex* extinct*" OR "sex* divers*" OR "sex* distribution*" OR "sex* disparit*" OR
"sex* differen*" OR "sex* determin*" OR "sex* dependen*" OR "sex* chromosome*" OR "sex*
character*" OR "sex* specific*" OR "sex* indicat*" OR "reproductive work*" OR "reproductive
right*" OR "reproductive health*" OR "sex* violen*" OR "sex* harass*" OR "sex* exploit*" OR
"sex* discriminat*" OR mother* OR boy OR girl OR father* OR "sex* trait*" OR "sex* health"
OR "sex* behavio*r" OR daughter OR parent*) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(biolog* w/3 sex) OR
TITLE-ABS-KEY(biomark* w/5 sex) OR TITLE-ABS-KEY(sex w/5 stratif*) AND DOCTYPE(ar
OR re OR cp OR sh OR dp) AND PUBYEAR IS 2020 AND NOT TITLE-ABS-KEY(*engender*)
```

For each of the 16 SDGs, a corpus consisting of the publications identified by queries described recently (Rivest, Kashnitsky, Bédard-Vallée, et al., 2021). was created from an analytical copy of the Scopus dataset accessed via ICSR Lab (ICSR Lab), snapshot dated March 1st 2021. A second corpus consisting of the publications identified by each SDG keyword search AND the selected sex and gender keyword search was created from the same data. This overlap was used as the basis for calculating the proportion of each SDG's publications that include those related to sex and/or gender research topics as well as for developing topical maps using VOSviewer (Version 1.6.17) (CWTS, 2021).

Owing to the processing limits of VOSviewer, where SDG publication sets were too large for mapping they have been randomly down-sampled to approximately 20,000 publications; this applies to all SDG publication sets except for SDGs 1, 5 and 14. In VOSviewer, we applied binary counting of terms, meaning that the presence or absence of a term in a publication was used for determining the occurrence frequencies and term co-occurrence. We applied a term occurrence threshold of at least 100 publications for inclusion in the map across each publication set with the exception of SDG 1, (the smaller volume of publications meant that a threshold of at least 50 publications was more appropriate). VOSviewer's default setting to map 60% of the most relevant terms (based on the calculated relevance score) was selected. To further validate the specificity of the sex and gender keyword search, we carefully examined the results of the approach described above for SDG 5: Gender Equality. We found the expected high degree of overlap between the SDG 5 publication set and those publications within it tagged as also being identified by the sex and gender keyword search.

Results

Most SDGs have a low proportion of publications related to sex and/or gender

The number of research publications in 2020 identified by each SDG query is shown in Table 2, along with the number and proportion of these that were also identified by the sex and gender keyword query. Most of the SDGs have a low proportion of publications that explicitly relate to sex and gender research topics. SDG 5: Gender Equality and SDG 3: Good Health and Well-being stand out for their relatively high shares (94% and 55%, respectively). Among the

remainder, no SDG has a share above 40% and eight are under 10%. This means that most research on SDGs does not include explicit consideration of sex and/or gender.

The ranking of the SDGs by proportion of sex and/or gender topical publications does align to some extent with the classification that the report from UN Women gave to the SDG indicator framework (UN Women, 2018). Each SDG was classified as “gender-sensitive”, “gender-sparse” or “gender-blind” to reflect how gender-specific the SDG indicators are. While the UN Women classification addressed gender (not sex), it is clear that the “gender-sensitive” SDGs tend to have the amongst the higher proportions of sex and gender publications, and the “gender-sparse” and “gender-blind” SDGs tend to have lower proportions.

Table 2: Proportion of SDG publications that include sex and gender keywords.

SDG No.	Sustainable Development Goal	Publications identified by SDG query	Publications ALSO identified by sex and gender keyword search	Proportion of SDG publications that include sex and gender keywords	SDG's UN Women gender classification
5	Gender Equality	25,107	23,587	94%	Gender-sensitive
3	Good Health and Well-being	395,528	216,342	55%	Gender-sensitive
16	Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions	34,392	13,277	39%	Gender-sensitive
10	Reduced Inequalities	38,638	13,837	36%	Gender-sensitive
1	No Poverty	13,740	4,093	30%	Gender-sensitive
4	Quality Education	34,702	8,489	24%	Gender-sensitive
2	Zero Hunger	35,658	6,870	19%	Gender-sparse
8	Decent Work and Economic Growth	40,718	5,589	14%	Gender-sensitive
15	Life on Land	34,943	2,911	8%	Gender-blind
11	Sustainable Cities and Communities	55,934	3,779	7%	Gender-sparse
14	Life Below Water	26,395	1,713	6%	Gender-blind
6	Clean Water and Sanitation	49,337	2,223	5%	Gender-blind
12	Responsible Consumption and Production	36,464	1,482	4%	Gender-blind
9	Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	57,565	1,729	3%	Gender-blind
13	Climate Action	43,151	1,282	3%	Gender-sparse
7	Affordable and Clean Energy	108,025	991	1%	Gender-blind

The term mapping approach allows us to examine topical clusters in the corpus of research relevant to each SDG, and to overlay this with a view on those clusters which explicitly include terms related to sex and/or gender, which represent publications on sex and gender research topics. In the following sections we will present a selection of these SDG maps.

SDG 5: Gender Equality has the expected high coverage of sex and gender relevant research

The term map created for SDG 5: Gender Equality is shown in Figure 1, and the topical clusters in Panel A (top) clearly reveal the diversity of research relevant to this SDG's targets and indicators. Major clusters of terms relating to gender in health on the right of the map and gender in social policy on the left are bridged by a cluster relating to the medical and policy literature around sexual abuse and exploitation appear at the top of the map. Panel B (bottom) illustrates the high degree of overlap (94% of publications per Table 2) between the SDG publication set and those publications within it tagged as also being identified by the sex and gender keyword search.

Sex and gender aspects of SDG 4: Quality Education are explicit in education practice but not education policy research

Pedagogy is the theory and practice of teaching and learning, and research relevant to this field is represented in the map for SDG 4: Quality Education shown in Figure 3 by four topical clusters visible in Panel A (top). The cluster on the right of the map represents terms dealing primarily with educational settings from early years through to high school; on the left, the focus is on tertiary education as well as vocational education and labour force outcomes. The cluster at the top of the map deals with issues relating to medical education.

SDG4 is classed as “gender-sensitive” by the UN Women report (UN Women, 2018) and for many years it has been known that formative educational experiences and educational attainment are different for boys and girls (Buchmann, DiPrete, & McDaniel, 2008). However, Panel B (bottom) appears to reflect sex and gender elements are included in publications addressing topics around early years, junior and senior school education (and to a lesser extent in medical education) but is almost absent from those parts of the map dealing with higher education or the effectiveness of classroom teaching.

Figure 3. SDG 4: Quality Education term map. Binary counting (present/absent, not count of occurrences) was applied to terms in titles and abstracts of 19,915 publications in 2020 (sampled from 34,702 in total), and those with at least 100 occurrences were mapped using VOSviewer. Node size indicates count of occurrences, and node proximity reflects frequency of co-occurrence (nodes close together co-occur more frequently than nodes far apart). In Panel A (top), colors indicate topical clusters; in Panel B (bottom), color scale indicates the proportion of publications associated with the mapped terms that were also identified by the sex and gender keyword search.

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